

ON THE ROLE OF THE INTERNAL AND SURFACE DEFECTS IN THE FATIGUE AND STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY OF ADDITIVELY MANUFACTURED 316L STAINLESS STEEL

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This study aims to clarify the effect of process-related defects on the fatigue integrity of additive manufacturing (AM) stainless steel 316 L. X-ray computed tomography (XCT) is used to characterise process-related defects' features and their synergistic interaction to define the effective defect size parameter $\sqrt{area_{eff}}$, leading to identifying potential sites for fatigue crack initiation before testing. The introduced equivalent defect size critical value is considered an initial semi-elliptic surface short crack in the critical defect-based fatigue crack growth model for the fatigue life prediction of AM components. The proposed single crack growth model demonstrates promise to be suited as an engineering approach for fatigue life prediction of AM components. This model shows a good correlation between XCT imaging in a temporal domain during fatigue testing and the predicted crack initiation and propagation phases for the tested AM 316L stainless steel samples.

Keywords: Additive manufacturing, Defect, Fatigue

INTRODUCTION

Metal AM has been developed fast in recent years to fabricate integrated components with complex geometries (Cooke et al. [1]). However, several challenges mainly induced during the manufacturing process limit the more widespread use of AM in different industries for various engineering applications. The metal AM processes involve complex multi-physics phenomena, making the fabricated parts prone to manufacturing defects, pores, and surface roughness (Sanaei [2]). These defects negatively influence the structural integrity of the metal AM components, especially in fatigue-critical load-carrying applications (Gockel et al. [3], Nafar Dastgerdi et al. [4]). Therefore, assessing the fatigue integrity of in-service metal AM components, including fatigue crack initiation and propagation and failure, is paramount.

XCT, a powerful non-destructive technique, enables three-dimensional observation and assessment of defects in metal AM components (Plessis et al. [5]). However, this technique is mainly employed to systematically characterise the internal defects of metal AM components (Luo et al. [6])

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and, in a few studies, manually characterise the surface defects (Plessis [7]). The authors have recently introduced a new determination algorithm able to describe and characterise the surface defects of complex metal AM components systematically using XCT measurements with the minimum possible error in image processing [4]. Besides, the new defects detection algorithm has been employed to characterise internal and surface defects' synergistic interaction to define the effective defect size parameter $\sqrt{area_{eff}}$, leading to identifying potential sites for fatigue crack initiation before testing. This new characterisation framework is also employed in this study to monitor the fatigue crack initiation and propagation based on measuring the variation in specimen surface topography in the axial and circumferential directions, providing further information into defects' growth and fatigue damage process.

Fracture mechanics-based methods for defect-based fatigue life prediction of AM components have been of great interest, as discussed extensively by Sanaei and Fatemi [8]. Most previous studies have only considered the internal defect size for defect-based modeling and prediction of fatigue strength of metal AM parts (Romano et al. [9], Pessard et al. [10]). However, the interaction effect of internal and surface defects should be considered. This paper highlights the importance of considering the interaction effect of process-related defects in the circumferential direction between different surface defects in the close vicinity and between the internal and surface defects in the radial direction to determine the critical equivalent defect size. This can be considered as an initial short crack in the critical defect-based fatigue crack growth model for the fatigue life prediction of AM components.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Material and specimen fabrication

This study used direct metal laser sintering as a powder bed fusion method to manufacture the stainless steel 316L specimens. The test specimens were fabricated using the EOS GmbH (M290) system. The powder was spherical, with an approximately average size of 37 μm in diameter. The dog bone-shaped round samples were produced vertically with the tensile axis and manufacturing direction parallel to the z-direction; see Figure 1. No post-process machining was conducted, and all specimens were fabricated to the net shape. Samples were made with a laser power of 250 W and a scanning speed of 1083 mm/s. The hatch distance was 90 μm , and the manufacturing layer thickness was 40 μm . The volumetric energy density was computed to be 64.12 J/mm³. The platform was pre-heated and kept at a constant 80 °C during manufacturing. Heat treatment was not carried out for the samples; however, significant residual stresses were not expected due to the small scanning chessboard island size, the platform's pre-heating, and the small size specimen and thickness which does not allow the development of large residual stresses (Waqar et al. [11]).

FIGURE 1. Geometry and dimensions of the manufactured vertical fatigue specimen.

Interrupted fatigue test and XCT imaging

The ex-situ XCT (4DXCT) was carried out to scan the defects (internal and surface) under fatigue loading to detect defects' growth and interaction, i.e. fatigue crack initiation and propagation. The XCT scanning was performed using General Electric (GE) Phoenix v|tome|x s machine with 5 μm pixel size. The X-ray tube acceleration voltage and power were set to 170 kV and 5.1 W, respectively. To absorb low-energy X-rays, a 0.5 mm copper filter was employed. The distance between layers for each scan was 5 μm. Scans were done with a single longitudinal position and a 360° rotation, circular trajectory. Scanning was carried out with 1s exposure time and by averaging two or three exposures per angular position. The region of interest for XCT imaging was the middle 10 mm of the specimen in the z-direction. This region is shown by the red rectangle in Figure 1. The 4DXCT was performed for two samples at stress amplitude 190 MPa using load-controlled uniaxial fatigue testing with a load ratio R = 0.1 and a loading frequency of 10 Hz. Table 1 shows the fatigue test interruptions and XCT scanning from the samples.

TABLE 1. Fatigue test interruptions and XCT scanning from two samples at a constant stress amplitude.

Sample 1-XCT, $\sigma = 190 \text{ MPa}$	Sample 2-XCT, $\sigma = 190 \text{ MPa}$
$N_{XCT1} = 0$	$N_{XCT1} = 0$
$N_{XCT2} = 72\ 000$	$N_{XCT2} = 72\ 000$
$N_{XCT3} = 76\ 000$	$N_{XCT3} = 92\ 000$
$N_{XCT4} = 87\ 000$	$N_{XCT4} = 97\ 000$
$N_{XCT5} = 95\ 000$	$N_{XCT5} = 99\ 500$
$N_{f,sample\ 1-XCT} = 104\ 003$	$N_{f,sample\ 2-XCT} = 103\ 149$

Defects characterisation and effective defect size

The XCT imaging data were analyzed using ThermoFisher PerGeos 2020.2 software to measure internal defects' volume and position. The internal defects' distribution throughout the specimen along the axis and around it at different radial angles has been investigated. Defects on the surface, usually referred to as surface roughness, are the other type of defects that should be characterised as a rough surface is intrinsic to AM due to the build process's layer-by-layer nature. For this purpose, the new surface defect determination algorithm was employed [4]. The internal defects' projected area in the plane transverse to the build direction, their distance from the surface, and the depth of valleys on this plane in the radial direction were chosen as the most important metrics in the current study. They must be characterised to define the effective defect size parameter ($\sqrt{area_{eff}}$), considering process-related defects' features ($\sqrt{area_D}$, and $\sqrt{area_R}$ or R_v , the prospective internal and equivalent surface roughness defect sizes) and their synergistic interaction (d_{R-D} is the shortest distance between two adjacent defects). Figure 2 shows schematically the process of the introduced approach by authors to determine $\sqrt{area_{eff}}$ [12].

To determine the initial short crack size correctly for the critical defect-based fatigue crack growth model, the effective defect size parameter, $\sqrt{area_{eff}}$, is essential and the maximum detected ones used as crack depth size, a , see Figure 3a. The identification of the other dimension of semi-elliptical crack geometry, $2c$, is based on surface roughness characterisation as depicted in Figure 3b. The center of the initial semi-elliptic crack is located on the sample surface at the corresponding critical location around the sample at corresponding height and angle corresponding to the $\sqrt{area_{eff_{max}}}$. The circumscribed ellipse requires to satisfy the following conditions: the major axis lies at a tangent to the surface, and by definition, the minor axis is shorter than the major axis. This condition leads to determining the other dimension of the semi-elliptical crack, c . It should be noted

that the interaction of the surface defects close to each other is also considered in defining the initial semi-elliptical crack geometry. Thus, the initial worst-case crack geometry is determined by considering the interaction of close defects in both dimensions, as shown in Figure 3b.

FIGURE 2. Schematic of the proposed approach to calculate $\sqrt{areaeff}$ (effective initial crack depth size), applied for sample 1-XCT [12].

FIGURE 3. (a) Schematic diagram of the geometrical parameters defining the surface semi-ellipse crack based on affecting parameters for defining $\sqrt{areaeff}$, and (b) schematic diagram of determining the initial worst-case crack geometry based on the interaction of close defects in both dimensions [12].

The Hartman–Schijve variant of the NASGERO crack growth equation is used to represent the growth of the initial semi-elliptic crack front defined based on the interaction of the process-related defects in the circumferential and axial direction, as follows [13]:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = D \left[\frac{\Delta K - 0.1}{\sqrt{1 - (1-R)A}} \right]^P \quad (1)$$

D, P are constants, $1.49 \times 10^{-10}, 1.99$. A is the cyclic fracture toughness, $69 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ [14]. R is stress ratio.

The stress intensity factor ΔK is specified for each representative growth point in semi-elliptical crack front using the equations by Newman and Raju [15] employed to the circular cross-section:

$$\Delta K_I = \lambda \Delta \sigma \sqrt{\frac{\pi a}{Q}} f(\phi)$$

$$Q = 1 + 1.464 \left(\frac{a}{c}\right)^{1.65}, \lambda = [1.13 - 0.09\left(\frac{a}{c}\right)] [1 + 0.1(1 - \sin\phi)^2] \quad (2)$$

$$f(\phi) = \left[\sin^2\phi + \left(\frac{a}{c}\right)^2 \cos^2\phi \right]^{1/4}$$

where $\Delta\sigma$ is the stress range.

Using this approach, the stress intensity factor of the crack front can be obtained continuously while considering the changes to the crack aspect ratio during fatigue loading. Thus, the progress of the crack's aspect ratio during its growth is considered in this model [12].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Defects characterisation approach is conducted for both samples. Since surface connected defects are critical potential sites for crack initiation, first surface roughness characterisation is carried out. Holistic information on the surface topologies of AM components was provided using quantitative parameters (e.g., R_a (arithmetic mean roughness) and R_z (the five largest peak-to-peak average roughness)), which could be measured for each surface profile around the sample. Figure 4a-d shows R_a and R_z distribution around sample 2-XCT and the exemplary surface profiles for this sample at specific angles before loading and after 99 500 cycles. This figure shows the interaction of the surface defects on the circumferential direction is critical when notches on different surface profiles are located in close vicinity with respect to the height at different angles. In this case, the dimension of the initial semi-elliptical crack on the circumferential direction, $2c$, is considerably higher than the other dimension along the radial direction, a , defined by $\sqrt{area_{eff}}$.

FIGURE 4. (a) The roughness average, R_a , (b) average maximum height of profile, R_z , distribution around the sample axis with 1° angle, 3D-sample' surface topologies (c) before loading and (d) after 99 500 cycles for specific intervals around the sample 2-XCT.

Defects' characterisation approach to determine the initial worst-case crack geometry based on the interaction of close defects in both dimensions is also conducted for sample 1-XCT as critical potential sites and $\sqrt{area_{eff}}$ in the radial direction are detected in Figure 2. In this case, the interaction of surface defects at this location has less interval in the circumferential direction at the same height compared to sample 1-XCT. Table 2 depicts the dimension and location of the initial worst-case crack geometry for both sample.

TABLE 2. The initial worst-case crack geometry size using the proposed defects determination algorithm based on the interaction of close defects in both dimensions.

Sample	θ (deg)	Height (z) (mm)	$a = \sqrt{\text{area}_{\text{eff,max}}}$ (mm)	$2c$ (mm)
XCT-1	97	5.65	0.129	0.610
XCT-2	134	4.23	0.110	0.820

The proposed critical defect-based fatigue crack growth model predicts the crack's propagation life. Thus, the sample's total fatigue life, $N_{f,model}$, can be determined by considering the initiation life of the short crack, $N_{initiation}$, and summing with the fatigue propagation life, $N_{p,model}$. Based on the experimental findings from the ex-situ fatigue test for each sample, the weight selection for $N_{initiation}$ has been considered to be 65% of the total life. This is consistent with the previous studies that reported a considerable fraction of the fatigue life was consumed in the initiation of small cracks (Tammis-Williams et al. [16] and Qian et al. [17]). It should be noted that the crack initiation step in the percentage of the total life is sensitive to the studied domain, and thus 65% of the total life is only valid in the high cycle domain of 10^6 cycles. The comparison of the predicted and experimental fatigue lives of the tested specimens in this work is presented in Table 3. It can be observed there is a good agreement between the predicted and experimental values. This finding also confirms the single crack model with an appropriate characterisation approach to detect the critical initial defect size as a short crack can be a practical approach for fatigue life prediction of metal AM parts. However, it may result in a non-conservative assessment since it cannot precisely consider the real multiple crack propagation phenomena, as a discrepancy between experiments and the model prediction results is reported in Table 3. Further study is still needed to propose a synergistic multiple-fatigue crack growth model in predicting the total fatigue life based on actual phenomena, as planned for future work.

TABLE 3. Comparison of the predicted and experimental fatigue life for samples.

Sample	$N_{p,model}$	$N_{initiation}$	$N_{f,model} = N_{p,model} + N_{initiation}$	$N_{f,exp} / N_{f,model}$
1-XCT $\sigma = 190 \text{ MPa}$	51 300	$0.65N_{f,model}$	146 571	0.71
2-XCT $\sigma = 190 \text{ MPa}$	45 100	$0.65N_{f,model}$	129 857	0.79

It should be noted in the vicinity of the predicted initial worst-case crack, there are other defects that can be potential sites for fatigue damage formation. Figure 5a-b shows the 3D rendering of fatigue cracks and the sample's front views after 95 000 cycles and for the upper part of the fractured sample 1-XCT. When two cracks are located off the same plane and during their growth, start to overlap, a fracture of the bridging ligament would happen, leading to ridges on the fracture surfaces. In this figure, black arrows show the possibility of cracks coalescence and ridges caused by the merging of multiple fatigue cracks extending on different planes.

FIGURE 5. (a) Rendered front view of sample 1-XCT at N=95 000 cycles, and (b) after breaking for the upper part using the damage detection algorithm based on the post-processing of the XCT data for detecting the surface profiles and calculating the surface roughness.

Detailed front view fractography of the upper part of the broken sample 1-XCT with higher magnification of two sites close to the ledges is examined to better elucidate the failure mechanism, as depicted in Figure 6. It can be seen that there is a shear dominant region at or close to ledges, which is perpendicular to the crack growth plane in opening mode. The crack growth mode is changed to the shear mode in this region.

FIGURE 6. Front view fractography of two sites close to the ridges on the upper part of the broken sample 1-XCT with higher magnification images.

The same analysis is conducted for sample 2-XCT as depicted in Figure 7a-c. The front view of the sample for $90 < \theta < 270$ at $N=99\,500$ cycles is shown in Figure 7c using the damage detection algorithm based on the post-processing of the XCT data for detecting the surface profiles and calculating the surface roughness proposed recently by the authors [4,12]. Four cracks at different heights around the sample are extended. The projection view of these cracks at $N=99\,500$ cycles is superposed onto the fracture surface of tested sample 2-XCT, as shown in Figure 7a. By comparing Figs. 7 a and 7c, it can be seen the formed crack 1 is due to the merging of multiple cracks on the slightly same height in close vicinity in the circumferential direction, as also expected from the detected surface defects before loading, see Fig 4b-c. In Figure 7c, crack 3 and crack 4 are merged at this stage of fatigue loading and there is tendency for coalescence of crack 2, crack 3, and crack 1, as shown in the front view of the broken sample in Figure 7b.

FIGURE 7. (a) Superposition of the projection of front view of the sample 2-XCT at $N=99\,500$ cycles showing crack growth step onto the fracture surface (b) front view fractography of the upper part of the broken sample 2-XCT, showing merged cracks, (c) front view of the sample 2-XCT at $N=99\,500$ cycles using the damage detection algorithm.

Detailed front view fractography of crack 2 on the broken sample 2- XCT is depicted in Figure 8 showing the shear dominant region during the merging of the cracks. Moreover, detailed scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images with higher magnification showing the crack initiation sites on crack 1 are depicted in Figure 9. It can be seen fatigue origins have been located at several locations around the sample axis ($90 < \theta < 200$) at almost the same heights as the merged crack 1 shown in Figure 7c. These multiple cracks coalesce during crack propagation forming a big crack on the fracture surface, speeding up fatigue failure.

FIGURE 8. Front view fractography of the damage location on the upper part of the broken sample 2-XCT and higher magnification images of crack 2 on the surface of the specimen in which damage was initiated and shear dominant region was formed between crack 2 and crack 3.

FIGURE 9. SEM top views of the fracture surface of the sample 2-XCT that failed due to surface features located roughly at the same plane. Higher magnification images showing the crack initiation sites.

CONCLUSION

This paper used XCT imaging during fatigue testing to provide further information on the fatigue crack initiation and propagation of AM stainless steel 316L parts. Results indicate the interaction effect of process-related defects in the circumferential direction between different surface defects in

the close vicinity and between the internal and surface defects in the radial direction is critical to define the equivalent defect size. A defect detection algorithm is employed for XCT imaging from the intact sample before testing to determine the equivalent defect size's critical value in both directions as an initial semi-elliptic surface short crack to be employed in the critical defect-based fatigue crack growth model for the fatigue life prediction of AM components. The introduced single crack growth model, by applying an appropriate characterisation approach to detect the initial semi-elliptic surface short crack based on defects' features and their interaction, demonstrates promise to be suited as an engineering approach for fatigue life prediction of AM components.

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Cooke, S., Ahmadi, K., Willerth, S., Herring, R., *J. Manuf. Process*, Vol. 57, 2020, pp. 978–1003.
- (2) Sanaei, N., Fatemi, A., *Prog. Mater. Sci*, Vol. 117, 2021, pp. 100724.
- (3) Gockel, J., Sheridan, L., Koerper, B., Whip, B., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 124, 2019, pp. 380–388.
- (4) Nafar Dastgerdi, J., Jaber, O., Remes, H., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 163, 2022, pp. 107025.
- (5) du Plessis, A., Yadroitsev, I., Yadroitsava I., Le Roux, S.G., *Addit. Manuf*, Vol. 5, 2018, pp. 227–247.
- (6) Luo, Q., Yin, L., Simpson, T.W., Beese, A.M., *Addit. Manuf*, Vol. 56, 2022, pp. 102915.
- (7) du Plessis, A., Beretta, S., *Addit. Manuf*, Vol. 35, 2020, pp. 101424.
- (8) Sanaei, N., Fatemi, A., *Prog. Mater. Sci*, Vol. 117, 2021, pp. 100724.
- (9) Romano, S., Brückner-Foitz, A., Brandao, A. Gumpinger, J., Ghidini, T., Beretta, S., *Eng. Fract. Mech*, Vol. 187, 2018, pp. 165–189.
- (10) Pessard, E., Lavialle, M., Laheurte, P., Didier, P., Brochu, M., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 149, 2021, pp. 106206.
- (11) Waqar, S., Guo, K., Sun, J., *Opt. Laser. Technol*, Vol 149, 2022, pp. 107806.
- (12) Nafar Dastgerdi, J., Jaber, O., Remes, H., Lehto, P., Hosseini Toudeshky, H., Kuva, J., *Addit. Manuf*, Vol. 70, 2023, pp. 103559.
- (13) Jones, R., Michopoulos, J.G., Iliopoulos, A.P., Singh Raman, R.K., Phan, N., Nguyen, T., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 116, 2018, pp. 10–22.
- (14) Iliopoulos, A., Jones, R., Michopoulos, J., Phan, N., Singh Raman, R.K., *Aerospace*, Vol. 5, 2018, pp. 118.
- (15) Newman, J.C., Raju, Jr.I.S., *Eng. Fract. Mech*, Vol. 15, 1981, pp. 185–192.
- (16) Tammis-Williams, S., Withers, P.J., Todd, I., Prangnell, P.B., *Sci. Rep*, Vol. 7, 2017, pp. 7308.
- (17) Qian, W., Wu, S., Wu, Z., Ahmed, S., Zhang, W., Qian, G., Withers, P.J., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 155, 2022, pp. 106616.